

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners' Network

**Deliverable D6.15 Policy paper on
areas require more standardisation
Public**

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	D6.15
Deliverable name	Policy paper on areas require more standardisation
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP6
Due date	30/04/2025
Version	1.0
Actual submission date	17/04/2025

Responsible organization	ASI
Editor(s)	Karl Grün, Jörg Nachbaur
Contributor(s)	-
Reviewers(s)	CENTRIC, GDCOC

Disclaimer	This document reflects only the view of its authors, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.
-------------------	--

DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	10/03/2025	Draft	Karl Grün, Jörg Nachbaur (ASI)	Initial Draft
0.2	04/04/2025	Draft	Karl Grün, Jörg Nachbaur (ASI)	Initial Draft completed and submitted to internal review
0.3	14/04/2025	Draft	CENTRIC, GDCOC	Feedback from internal reviewers
0.4	15/04/2025	Draft	ASI	Comments from internal reviewers resolved and draft version submitted to Project Coordinator
1.0	17/04/2025	Final	Klaudia Kaczmarek (PPHS)	Final approval and submission

Table of Contents

- Table of Contents 3
- 1. Summary..... 4
- 2. Overview of CYCLOPES 5
- 3. EU Policy Environment for Standardisation in the area of Security and Cybercrime 6
- 4. Embedding standardisation needs within the EU policy environment 8

1. Summary

This deliverable considers the needs expressed by practitioners requiring standardisation through the CYCLOPES project and views them through a policy lens.

Firstly, we discuss commonalities between the EU policy and legal environment and the topics explored through the CYCLOPES desktop research and workshops on standardisation, identifying synergies and complementarities. Secondly, we take the publicly available gaps and needs identified across the five pillars of technology, process, people, organisation and legal and highlight where these align with forthcoming and proposed policy actions and where further investment may be required to better support practitioners through standards.

2. Overview of CYCLOPES

The HORIZON 2020 project CYCLOPES (Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners Network) aims to build a stable European network of law enforcement agencies to effectively combat cybercrime. It is a five-year network project with 21 partners from 14 different EU countries. The partners come from EU law enforcement agencies, research institutes, universities and companies. The lead lies with the Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS). The project started in May 2021.

In addition to setting up the network, the core of the project is the joint transfer of knowledge to security authorities and participation in standardisation recommendations. In thematically predefined user workshops, gaps and requirements, but also the current status of the authorities for combating cybercrime, are determined. A list of priorities with an increased need for standardisation is also created. The workshops are held three times a year on the overarching subject areas:

- Cybercrime – Affecting People Directly
- Cybercrime – Affecting Systems
- Digital Forensics

The outcomes of the workshops lead to a list of available tools, software and research opportunities that may help address some of the gaps, needs and challenges identified for each thematic area. Each year, one workshop provides the inspiration for a Joint Live Exercise – an opportunity for solution providers and practitioners to come together to trial available solutions linked to the gaps and challenges identified.

The purpose of this deliverable is to produce a policy paper on areas in cybercrime and digital forensics requiring more standardisation.

Our approach considers the EU policy environment in the field of cybercrime and digital forensics in correlation with the standardization recommendations resulting from the needs expressed in practitioners' workshops and further developed in annual standardisation workshops with high-level representatives of the standardisation communities, as well as further research in CYCLOPES.

3. EU Policy Environment for Standardisation in the area of Security and Cybercrime

On a global level the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade of the World Trade Organisation (WTO TBT Agreement¹) defines the principles for standardisation which are transparency, openness, impartiality and consensus, effectiveness and relevance, coherence and development dimension. The TBT Agreement aims to ensure that standards are non-discriminatory and do not create unnecessary obstacles to trade. At the same time, it recognises WTO members' right to implement measures to achieve legitimate policy objectives, such as the protection of human health and safety, or protection of the environment. The TBT Agreement strongly encourages members to base their measures on international standards as a means to facilitate trade. Through its transparency provisions, it also aims to create a predictable trading environment.

In the European Union the legal framework for standardisation is Regulation (EU) 1025/2012² on European standardisation, amended by Regulation (EU) 2022/2480³. The purpose of this regulation is to support EU policies and law through standardisation and to ensure a balanced representation of stakeholders in the European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs). The ESOs recognised by the regulation are CEN (European Committee for Standardisation), CENELEC (European Electrotechnical Committee for Standardisation) and ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute).

Even 88% of European Standards developed in CEN and CENELEC are proposed by the market (manufacturers, testing houses, etc.), the remaining 12 % are developed based on standardisation requests from the European Commission. These 12% are so-called “harmonised Standards” (hEN). Manufacturers, other economic operators, or conformity assessment bodies can use hEN to demonstrate that products, services, or processes comply with relevant EU legislation.

One example is EN 17529:2022, *Data protection and privacy by design and by default*, which was elaborated under the European Commission’s standardisation request M/530 – C(2015)⁴. Another example is the multi-part EN 18031:2024, *Common security requirements for radio equipment*, elaborated under the European Commission’s standardisation request M/588 – C(2022)6574⁵.

¹ https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tbt_e/principles_standards_tbt_e.htm

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2012/1025/oj/eng>

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2480/oj/eng>

⁴ COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION of 20.1.2015 on a standardisation request to the European standardisation organisations as regards European standards and European standardisation deliverables for privacy and personal data protection management pursuant to Article 10(1) of Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council in support of Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and in support of Union’s security industrial policy. https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/mandate/530_en

⁵ COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION of 23.8.2023 amending Implementing Decision C(2022) 5637 on a standardisation request to the European Committee for Standardisation and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation as regards radio equipment in support of Directive 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/30. https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/mandate/585Amd1_en

The most recent standardisation request related to Cybersecurity is M/606 – C(2025)618⁶. This standardisation request is in support of the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) which aims to enhance EU cybersecurity by ensuring that digital products and services remain secure throughout their lifecycle. It promotes proactive risk management and accountability, enabling businesses and users to collaborate in building a safer digital future. To support CRA implementation, the European Commission has issued a standardisation request to the European Standardisation Organisations, focusing on both horizontal standards for a generic framework and vertical standards for specific product risks.

Cybersecurity involves protecting network and information systems (NIS), their users, and other affected individuals from cyber incidents and threats. To respond to the increased exposure of Europe to cyber threats, Directive 2022/2555⁷, also known as NIS2, replaced its predecessor, Directive 2016/1148 or NIS1. NIS2 raises the EU common level of ambition on cybersecurity, through a wider scope, clearer rules and stronger supervision tools. It requires Member States to enhance their cybersecurity capabilities, while introducing risk management measures and reporting requirements to entities from more sectors and setting up rules for cooperation, information sharing, supervision, and enforcement of cybersecurity measures.

Even there are no formal standardisation requests based on NIS2, next to several references to Cybersecurity standards developed by ISO and IEC in NIS2, Article 25 of the NIS2 Directive encourages EU Member States to use European and International Standards and technical specifications relevant to the security of network and information systems. In the same Article the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) is requested to draw up advice and guidelines regarding already existing standards which would allow for those areas to be covered.

CEN and ENISA signed a cooperation agreement in 2013. This cooperation agreement⁸ covers the dissemination and promotion of information on publications, results, meetings, seminars. CEN is also represented in ENISA's Advisory Group⁹.

In the context of digital forensics, forensic laboratories are accredited based on the (harmonised) EN ISO/IEC 17025, *General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories*. This European Standard (which is the identical adoption of the International Standard ISO/IEC 17025) was developed following the European Commission's Standardisation Mandate M/417 addressed to CEN, CENELEC, and ETSI for the use of Harmonised Standards in support of the new legal framework and sectoral certification scheme. This Standardisation Request (previously called Mandat) relates to Regulation (EC)

⁶ COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION of 3.2.2025 on a standardisation request to the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (Cenelec) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) as regards products with digital elements in support of Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Cyber Resilience Act).
https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/mandate/606_en

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022L2555>

⁸ See <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/cyber-security-collaboration-agreement-between-enisa-european-standardisation-bodies-cen-and-cenlec>

⁹ See <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/about-enisa/structure-organization/advisory-group>

No 765/2008¹⁰ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 July 2008 setting out the requirements for accreditation and market surveillance relating to the marketing of products.

4. Embedding standardisation needs within the EU policy environment

CYCLOPES has run workshops each aligned with one of the three pillars of the project – digital forensics, cybercrime affecting systems, and cybercrime affecting people directly. These workshops identify practitioners' challenges, gaps and needs across five key areas: technical, people, organisational, legal and process. These needs were assessed regarding how these needs can be met by standardisation. This is done either by making practitioners aware of the existence of already available standards or – in the absence of such standards – to elaborate recommendations for standardisation. Annual reports on standardisation recommendations also complement these activities as part of CYCLOPES WP4.

The following topics – structured according to the before describes pillars – were analysed and evaluated with regard to areas where standardisation is needed:

- Digital Forensics:
 - Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies (see D4.2¹¹)
 - Automotive Digital Forensics (see D4.3¹²)
 - Internet of Things (IoT) as a facilitator of cybercrime (see D4.4¹³)
 - Enhancing Digital Forensic Investigations using OSINT/Cyber Intelligence (see D4.5¹⁴)
- Cybercrime affecting People:
 - Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime (see D4.3)
 - Cloud Services in the context of cybercrime (see D4.4)
 - Fighting the Misuse of VR-Technologies and Use of Generative AI to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM) (see D4.5)
- Cybercrime affecting Systems:
 - Cybercrime relating to Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies (see D4.3)
 - Cryptocurrency as a facilitator for Cybercrime (see D4.4)
 - Business model of ransomware, including Crime-as-a-Service (see D4.5)

¹⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2008/765/oj/eng>

¹¹ CYCLOPES Deliverable 4.2, 1st Annual standardisation recommendations

¹² CYCLOPES Deliverable 4.3, 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations

¹³ CYCLOPES Deliverable 4.4, 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations

¹⁴ CYCLOPES Deliverable 4.5, 4th Annual standardisation recommendations

Based on the findings of these activities, which are included in more detail in the Annual Standardisation Recommendations of CYCLOPES, the following are extracted to propose policy actions, including further investment, in order to better support practitioners through standards.

One type of policy action on European level might be the process for the drafting of Annual Union Work Programme (AUWP) on European Standardisation. This AUWP contains an overview of all requests for standards which the European Commission intends to submit to European Standardisation Organisations.

Raising awareness about available standards supporting practitioners

It was recognised that most of the needs expressed by practitioners can be met by existing standards. To exploit the full potential of these standards “use-cases” describing which standards might be used for which investigation case would be of huge benefit.

These use-cases can be either included as informative Annexes in a related standard (e.g. ISO/IEC 27037, *Information technology — Security techniques — Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence*), or be summarised in a European Standardisation Deliverable as a Guidance document (e.g. CEN/CENELEC Technical Report).

Already in Article 25 of the NIS2 Directive EU Member States are encouraged to use European and International Standards and technical specifications relevant to the security of network and information systems. This awareness raising campaign can be supported by the European Commission together with ENISA in close cooperation with the European Standardisation Organisations.

Lack of standards that define requirements and test methods for digital forensics tools

In compliance with EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017, Clause 6.4.1 *a laboratory shall have access to equipment (including, but not limited to, measuring instruments, software, measurement standards, reference materials, reference data, reagents, consumables or auxiliary apparatus) that is required for the correct performance of laboratory activities and that can influence the results.*

The need for (standardised) criteria for tools used in digital forensics was addressed several times.

Already the CEN Workshop Agreement CWA 17865:2022¹⁵, *Requirements and Guidelines for a complete end-to-end mobile forensic investigation chain*, describes good practice and guidance for the selection and use of mobile forensic tools and provides a quick overview of points in different Annexes to consider when selecting a mobile forensic tool.

Even with this, there is a lack of standardisation of digital forensic tools. As an illustrative example, standard(s) for specifying criteria and requirements of deepfake detection tools to be used in investigations fighting the Misuse of VR Technologies and use of Generative AI to generate CSAM are needed to enable trustworthy selection of such tools. To verify the compliance of tools with the criteria/requirements, performance test methods are also required

¹⁵ https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/RI/cwa17865_2022.pdf

together with the definition of the quality of test data sets, and these can be also subject to standardisation.

Another important aspect is the use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine-Learning in digital forensics. Even there are ongoing European standardisation activities (some of the under the European Commission's Standardisation Request M/593 – C(2023)3215¹⁶) there is no specific activity supporting the use of such technologies in forensic examinations. Routine procedures can be performed by AI but in certain cases human elements (supervision) will always be needed to ensure important ethical and societal aspect are considered and followed. Furthermore, the use of AI in court trial processes, incl. forensics, is subject to the EU Artificial Intelligence Act¹⁷. For such AI and ML tools further research might be needed.

To verify that digital tools provided by different vendors and used in digital forensics meet standardised criteria, reliable testing is needed. This can be addressed in a standard specifying the criteria/requirements of tools and defining the test procedures to verify that the tool(s) meet the requirements. Based on that this can be used for conformity assessment purposes, e.g. the vendor can issue a self-declaration or involves a certification body for issuing a certificate for the tool.

Such a required standardisation should take into account the work performed by the NIST Computer Forensics Tool Testing Program (CFTT¹⁸). The goal of this program is to establish a methodology for testing computer forensic software tools by development of general tool specifications, test procedures, test criteria, test sets, and test hardware. The results provide the information necessary for toolmakers to improve tools, for users to make informed choices about acquiring and using computer forensics tools, and for interested parties to understand the tools capabilities.

A similar program on European level is the European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA)¹⁹. which purpose is the development of technological solutions for European Law Enforcement Agencies and Forensic Laboratories to use them in their fight against crime. Members of the Association are European Law Enforcement Agencies, Ministries of Interior, forensic institutes, and other European public security practitioners as well as relevant research technology organisations and industrial partners.

With this, a policy action requesting the elaboration of European Standards defining requirements and test methods for digital forensics tools is highly recommended.

Processes

Practitioners reported that the legal framework cannot keep pace with rapidly evolving cybercrime. A framework is needed to expedite the updating of legislation, enabling the integration of cyber considerations into existing laws much more swiftly than the current process allows for the introduction or amendment of legislation.

¹⁶ COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION of 22.5.2023 on a standardisation request to the European Committee for Standardisation and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation in support of Union policy on artificial intelligence, https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/mandate/593_en

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689>

¹⁸ <https://www.nist.gov/itl/ssd/software-quality-group/computer-forensics-tool-testing-program-cftt>

¹⁹ <https://www.eactda.eu/>

It is recognised, the topic of speeding up process time facing legal constraints is not in the sphere of influence of (voluntary) standardisation – even if technical standards, e.g. for data exchange, efficient reporting and documentation, are in place.

Practitioners prioritised the Mutual Legal Assistance Treaty process as the most critical one. It is recommended to review the MLAT process to determine opportunities for simplifying and expediting it, including the introduction of time limits and making use of opportunities for automation. In this context, practitioners raised the need for a uniformed reporting template for data to be disclosed when they issue a MLAT subpoena.